

Employees Crafting Favorable Working Conditions – Triple Loop Learning in the Higher Education Sector

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1. Scientific and practitioners' research presentations
 - a. Bottom-up and community-driven interventions

Purpose

The aim of this presentation is to offer new insights into how organizations may learn through the course of continuous and systematic interventions for mental health and wellbeing in the higher education sector. By ensuring that lessons, or experience, regarding organizational interventions, are harvested within the organization to support future change efforts the organization is building a learning capability (triple-loop-learning) (Von Thiele Schwarz et al., 2020). In this study, we address this triple loop learning through 1) exploring how the organizations have worked to improve both their intervention targets and their intervention work, and, 2) by looking deeper into the mechanisms behind transferring experiences from one intervention process to another, thus, continuously improving both the work environment and their intervention work.

The uniqueness of this study is twofold. 1) Researchers normally leave the organization after the evaluation of the change process is completed. The longitudinal process studied offers the opportunity to investigate a circular process of change as it plays out for the fourth and even 5th time. 2) The importance of learning and learning transfer are amplified in a sector where central stakeholders are employed on fixed term contracts experiencing extraordinary challenges with making sure valuable lessons are not lost while continuously operating to improve their work environment.

Design

The organization studied in this project is a Norwegian University that has been using the research-based intervention program, ARK (Norwegian abbreviation for work environment and climate survey, see Innstrand, Christensen, Undebakke, & Svarva, 2015) to screen and develop their psychosocial work environment continuously for more than 10 years. The ARK intervention program is built around the suggested five phases of Nielsen, Randall, Holten, & Rial-Gonzalez (2010) as a framework for the processual work with organizational mental health and well-being interventions, including 1) preparation, 2) screening, 3) development of action plans, 4) implementation, and 5) evaluation of interventions. ARK is currently being used by 23 universities and university colleges across Norway, and in two units in Sweden. Finally, ARK includes a database of more than 55.000 responses from all surveys conducted within the program. In this project the ARK intervention program is used as a framework for exploring some departments that have succeeded with continuous and systematic intervention work.

We have been cooperating with the university and faculty work environment coordinators to detect and reach out to units that has succeeded with their intervention work. Initial contact was established with the leader of the underlying units (departments and units). The leaders forwarded the invitation to participate in the study to all the employees in the respective units.

Data were collected through interviews as recommended by Nielsen & Randall (2013) in order to reveal the participants mental models (experiences) regarding the success of the intervention process. Mohammed, Ferzandi, and Hamilton (2010) argue that focus groups are a powerful method to reveal whether shared experiences have developed. Thus, the interviews were conducted in focus groups (N=38), consisting of either leaders (n=14; initiators), key stakeholders (n=12; executives), or employees (n=12; experiencers), working with the work environment in the 4 chosen units. The sample consisted of employees of different age, gender, and academic positions. Lastly, the data were analyzed in accordance with the framework of Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) to provide knowledge about the groups shared experiences of the intervention work.

Results

Preliminary results indicate that the main factor of success behind sustainable intervention work for mental health and well-being may be enabling, motivation and steering employee participation. Abildgaard et al. (2018) suggested 4 forms of participation, namely participation in content, process, the directness of the participation and participation as a goal in itself. We find support for the latter as a key for successful and sustainable intervention work. In these organizations the individual employee is motivated and enabled to improve their own working conditions in line with their actual needs. To enable and motivate for this behavior to last, the organizations have worked to create a culture of improvement, cooperation and knowledge sharing. In these organizations the focus is on employees getting to know one another and acknowledge the organizations diversity. This makes the employees more likely to work together to combine strengths and abilities in diverse groups of complementing competencies which effectively reduces the strain of a demanding and complex job. By embracing that progress comes from trial and error and that challenges are something to be shared, employees are invigorated to take initiative and improve their work situation together. To facilitate, the management has to enable, motivate and set the course for this collective continuous improvement of the work environment. Leaders must provide the necessary resources and act as role models that trusts their employees to do a good job and to collectively cocreate the environment that best enables them to do this. To ensure such processes the organizations have developed policies and practices that embraces the importance of the organization, leader, group and individual level for employees to use their strengths and abilities to improve their own working conditions and thereby mental health and wellbeing in line with the goals of the organization.

Implications

This study contributes to the knowledge on participation in research on organizational interventions for mental health and wellbeing by elaborating on what is necessary on the individual, group, leader and organizational level to facilitate for forms of participation that enables sustainable intervention work. In addition, the results from this study provides some important findings regarding how managers and practitioners in academia can work to motivate employees to create their own favorable working conditions, granting them with the best opportunity to stay healthy, happy and productive.

Acknowledgments

[ARK \(arbeidsmiljø og klimaundersøkelser\)](#)